

The Emotional Expressions of Rakti Rāga Bēgaḍa – A Brief Musicological Analysis

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Abstract:

Indian Classical Rāga is considered to be synonymous to the emotional expression. Every rāga carries a certain emotional expression and when rightly tuned in lyrics, gives the complete form of understanding the right expression. Bēgaḍa is a delightful rāga in Karnāṭik Music ranging its complete structural formation between 17th to 19th centuries. This rāga is truly in the sense categorized as a rakti rāga, for its rich essence of bhāva produced beyond the mere structure of the rāga. Usually, one can find this way of rāga development in Hindustani style rather than in the Karnāṭik system. This paper focuses on the emotional expressions of Bēgaḍa through musicological analysis including the interpretation and analysis on the usage of svara patterns, gamakās and the rasa aspects produced in the rāga through some of its compositions, establishes the scope of the research. The history based lakṣaṇa grandhās, the modern available literature as well as the available audio sources and music notations of the compositions are the Methodological resources for taking up this research with an expected Findings on the emotional landscape produced by this raga touching upon its innate rakti nature. This paper aims at the deeper understanding of the emotional expressions through insightful and analytical observation on the svarās and svara patterns of the rāga.

Keywords: Begada, Rakti Raga, emotional expression, musicological analysis, compositions.

Introduction

Bēgaḍa is predominantly a weighty rāga among many rāgās of Karnāṭik Music. It truly shows the real classism of the south Indian system of music. A unique rakti rāga¹ which produces the complete classical delight with its weighty appearance. Going beyond its mere

¹ Sangīta Sampradāya pradarśini - Page 115

parental structure, embracing the anya svara too beautifully within, shows the dynamism of the rāga in producing an emotional landscape. Usually in Karnātik music system one can find very rare number of rāgās undergo this unique development, whereas in Hindustāni it is a common appearance. Being a bhāṣānga and a rakti rāga, Bēgada has a vast scope in rāga ālāpa exploration.

Emotional expressions in a rāga can be identified through the analytical observation on the movement of the svarās, relation between the svarās intertwining with the aspect of gamaka and also through the concept of the sāhitya bhava in the compositions. Before going into the framework of the Musicological Analysis, let us now look at the historical perspectives of this rāga.

Historical Perspective of Bēgada

Bēgada rāga was said to be seen from the period of Annamayya, Purandaradāsa and then Kṣētrayya through their compositions and it was around 15th to 17th Century². The mentioning of this rāga was seen in Lakṣaṇagrāndhās from 17th century in the Rāga Lakṣaṇa of Muddu Vēnkaṭamakhi till 19th Century Sangīta Sāmpradāya Pradarśini, where the structure of the rāga was established upon reference to the Raga Lakshanasangraha by Hema Ramanathan.

³ Lakṣaṇagrāndha	Time period
Rāga Lakṣaṇam (RL-MV)	17 th Century
Sangraha Cūḍāmaṇi (SCh)	18 th Century
Sangīta Śāstrasāra Sangrahamu (SSS)	19 th Century
Mahābhārata cūḍāmaṇi (MBC)	18 th – 19 th Century
Rāgalakṣana (RL)	18 th – 19 th Century
Sangīta Sampradāyapradarśini (SSP)	19 th Century

²Sriram V, “Dr R S Jayalakshmi on Begada”, sriramv.com

³ Raga Lakshanasangraha, Page: 2-100

The historical mentions noted this raga as the janya of Śankarābharaṇam only and the usage of kaiśika niṣādam can be observed as a development of the rāga through its unique features while exploring the rāga svarūpa. Though śuddha madhyamaṁ is said to be handled a bit higher than its original place, it couldn't reach till prati madhyamaṁ and establish as an anya svara. It is an interesting point to note that the flavour of bēgaḍa extended so much with kaiśika niṣādam but couldn't attempt to reach prati madhyamaṁ like in behāg. The present-day structure of mūrcana was established in the period of Sangīta cūḍāmaṇi. Analysing the Kṣētrayya padaṁ shows the presence of kaiśika niṣādam from the pre- trinity period and also in the Muddu Vēnkaṭamakhi's raga lakṣaṇam (17th century) this raga was mentioned as a Bhāṣāṅga and rakti rāga⁴.

Definition of Rakti rāga

The term Rakti rāga comes from the classification of rāgās as Ghana Naya Dēśya, in which the Naya rāgās are also called Rakti rāgās or Mārga rāgās. The word Rakti had its roots from Sanskrit and means *pleasingness, charmingness, loveliness, attachment, affection, loyalty, devotion etc*⁵.

Rāgalakṣaṇa of Muddu Vēnkaṭamakhi, a commentary by R Sathyanarayana the explanation on Naya rāga is given as “*Naya raga earned connote qualities of smoothness, tenderness, delicateness, subtlety, finesse and charm in the presentation of the raga bhava. It attracts the listeners mind and affords aesthetic enjoyment.*”⁶ From this definition of Rakti rāga, one can understand how the texture of a rakti rāga will be.

Classifying Bēgaḍa as a rakti rāga seems to be apt from the understanding on the definitions of the rakti rāga. The rasa aspect of Bēgaḍa is an important point to discuss. It is noted from sources that it emanates Adbhuta, śrngāra, hāśya, devotion and vīra rasās⁷

The popular idiom Bēgaḍa Mīgaḍa should also be discussed at this point. It is not just adding the rhyme but means truly with the texture of the rāga. The word mīgaḍa means the cream formed on the warm milk which is very smooth. Being a rakti rāga with a characteristic of smoothness makes this idiom right.

⁴ Ragalakshanam of Muddu Venkatamakhi, Commentary by R Sathyanarayana

⁵ DDSA: The Practical Sanskrit English Dictionary

⁶ Ragalakshanam of Muddu Venkatamakhi, Commentary by R Sathyanarayana

⁷ Raga Begada - <http://carnatica.in/newsletter/begadanewsletter.htm>

A Musicological Analysis on the emotional expression through Bēgaḍa svarās

Analysis of the Bēgaḍa svarās:

Mūrcana: **s g r g m p d p ś / s g r g m p d n d p ś**
ś n₃ d p m, g r s / s n₂, d p m, g r s

As a janya of Śankarābharaṇaṁ rāga, the svarās present in Bēgaḍa are Ṣaḍjaṁ, Catuṣṛti Riṣabhaṁ, Antara Gāndhāraṁ, Śuddha Madhyamaṁ, Pancamaṁ, Kākali Niṣādaṁ and Kaiśiki Niṣādaṁ.

The role and handling of each svāra, the relation with the other svarās connecting through gamakās, the special prayōgās, the emotion each svāra carries will be presented, as a humble musicological analysis through musical observation, as follows:

❖ Ṣaḍjaṁ:

- The svāra ṣaḍjaṁ when observed as a graha svāra plays a very supportive role to take up an elongated **g** and in establishing the rāga svarūpa
 - Supportive Ṣaḍjaṁ: **s s g r g ...**
- When observed as more of the nyāsa role of the Ṣaḍjaṁ, the range of sangatīs between the **s** and **p**, often rest on **s** producing the *feel of completion of a statement*. This svāra gives a sort of *royal feel* when sung in combo with its close friend **r**.
 - Royalness of Ṣaḍjaṁ: **r s....**
m , m, g r, s...
- As a nyāsa, when it comes in combo with pañcamaṁ going up and down, the presence of Ṣaḍjaṁ makes it *feel secured* to its 5th as a consonant note and results in a very *rakti or the ranjaka mood*. Those sadja pancama sangatīs gives a lot of *aesthetical pleasure* to listen especially at the tāra sthāyi. The elongated ṣaḍjaṁ at tāram is the ultimate experience followed by the combination of sangatīs with pancamaṁ
 - Security of Sadjaṁ: **p d p ś ... \ (d)p.. – r r ś ś; \ (d) p – p ś m ġ r ś**
ś; \ (d) p ś; n p d, p / r ś;

The above-mentioned expressions are widely seen in the compositions and it is surprising to find that mostly the beginning sections of few compositions showcase all the above said expressions of the svara Ṣaḍjaṁ in Bēgaḍa. For example:

1. The first line of Pallavi in *Inta calamu jēsite varṇam* by Sri Veena Kuppayyar

Royalty	Security	Supportive
d p m , g r s , in . . . ta	r ṇ ḍ p ḍ p s , ca la.	s , s s g r g , mu . . . jē

2. The first line of Pallavi *Śankari nīve* by Sri Subbaraya Sastrī

ḍ p s s r , s , ; rr sṇ ḍ p s s g r g , mm grs , śan. ka ri nī. va ni śan.ka ri nī. . . va ni.
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Likewise, the expression of Ṣaḍjaṁ can also be seen in some other compositions in the beginning lines like in the *padam ēla padarēme*, *Lōkāvanacatura* kṛti. This svara also lends space to kākali niṣādam to happily depend and swing as one can observe **n** in handling of **s** itself.

❖ Antara Gāndhāraṁ:

- The Antara Gāndhāraṁ is the jīva and amśa svara of the rāga. One can observe the ālāpana starting at a long **g** note gives a *very pleasant feel* and the rāga prastāra at gāndhāra results in deep upāsana prakriya. Is this flavour of svara **g** inspired Sri Tyagaraja to compose *Nādōpāsana* kṛti in this rāga? It is a question to ponder.
- Interesting point to note is the antara **g** in this rāga is missing the friendship of śuddha **m** as it has usually to stick on like in Śankarābharaṇa and sits very strongly in its position in Bēgaḍa. Whether the direct and plain note or a hit from **s** or its establishment with the pattern **ss g r g** ,... its very stable as a long note *producing very deep nādam*.

g...; m g r s n s g... m g r s n d p p s g... s s g r g ...

- The steady role played by **g** helped śuddha **m** to move very vibrantly in such a way that it moved beyond its original position, which is the special feature of this rāga showing its rakti nature.

g m̃ - d p m̃ g r s

In the compositions like *padam Ēla padarēme, Śankari nīve, Lōkāvānacatura* one can find **g** as a long note.

❖ **Catuśṛti Riṣabham:**

- This svara is more of a *connecting nature*, but plays a very vital role in the structural formation of this raga. If this svara is completely removed in the ascent as mentioned by Muddu Venkatamakhi, one can imagine how the raga would be directly starting as **s g m**. The presence of **r** in *vakra* is the main feature of this raga.

s g r g

- Also, **r** involves in a very unique phrase with **s** varja in the phrase **ṛ n d p** which is seen in many compositions which gives a very *charming effect* like a *sparkling light* and flows smoothly.

❖ **Śuddha Madhyamam:**

- The svara **m** is the *rāga chāya svara* and has a lot of significance in this *rāga*. It has got a very special attention as *Bēgaḍa madhyamam*⁸ and is one of the notes which shows the *weighty nature* of this *rāga* in a smooth nature.
- There are different shades of *madhyama svara* as we observe in many compositions. One with a small oscillation like in the starting of *nādōpāsana kṛti* showing something like a *pleasing expression*, the over swinging oscillation touching 1 *śṛti* higher to its original but doesn't settle in *prati madhyama* positions, *showing a kind of loyalty*, it has in this raga and a kind of flat nature while singing in the phrase like **d m, g r s** with *pancama varja* expressing *some kind of affection*. All these shades produce a kind of *rakti* or *ranjakatva*.

Pleasing: **m, ; ~ m g g**, (as the phrase *nādōpāsana*..)

Loyalty: **p m̃, ; p**; (as in *caraṇa* in *Inta Calamu varṇam*), **mm̃ g r s**

Affection: **dm,grs** (as in *Bēgaḍa muktāyi svaram* in *Navarāgamālika varṇam*)

❖ **Pancamam:**

- This svara again takes mostly the role of *nyāsa*. This is like a resting note, where the journey of exploring the *ālāpāna* at *mandra sthāyi* and sort of long

⁸ Raga Nidhi, Page:73

note on **g**, exploring the different shades of madhyamaṁ, the musician takes **p** as a resting note again to dive deeper into the other part of rāga ālāpana.

- One can observe how Sri Tyagaraja has shown this pattern of utilising **p** as nyāsaṁ in many of his compositions especially in the pallavi itself. The compositions *nādōpāsana*, *tanvāri tanamu*, *nī padapankajamula*, *gaṭṭi gānu nanu*.

❖ **Catuśṛti Daivatam:**

- This svara is again like the svara **r** which is more of a connecting nature rather than any individual importance.
- Only involved in a zig zag appearance in ascent and flows down in a normal order in descent. It just stands as a strong shade to connect **s** and kākali **n** to **p** in descent and **p** to **s** in ascent.

ś (n) \ d p – p d p ś

- The support of **d** in handling kaiśika niṣādam is something one shouldn't forget, especially in the phrase **p d n, d p**. at times it feels like kaiśika niṣādam was born out of trying to give importance to this svara catuśṛti **d** in this rāga
- It seems like Sri Tyagaraja wanted to show how important is the svara **d** and started the kṛti *nī pada pankajamula* with an elongated **d, ; p, ; m, ; .**

❖ **Kākali & Kaiśiki Niṣādams:**

- The Nāyaka svara of Bēgaḍa is **n**. Bringing the classification into bhāṣānga rāga, this svara is really a playful one. This type of rāgās stands as examples as whether developing the rāga should be based on structure or based on the bhāva emanating by experiencing the rāga dēvata.
- The Hindustāni system embraces this type of rāga development in a more fluid manner, but having this unique type of rāgās few in number shows the maintenance of the discipline in our system.
- The pulling gamaka used on svarās **n** and **m** is the special feature of this raga. A humble thought to present here is that the kaiśika niṣādam being the 5th consonant śṛti of śuddha madhyamaṁ, the elongated m might be the inspiration to take the elongated pulling gamaka on **n**. we have few consonant phrases like:
n, dp – m, grs / n,n, dp – m, m, grs / m,, p d p

s – n,, s g r g (s and g are resting notes)

- The usage of both niṣādās can be seen in the compositions of Sri Dikshitar in compositions like Vallabha nāyakaśya, Tyāgarājāya namaste as well as in the compositions of Sri Tyagaraja also.

Special Prayōgās of Bēgaḍa emphasizing the Rakti nature of the Rāga:

Special prayōgās are those which give an add on flavour to the rāga mostly go beyond the structure of the rāga. Bēgaḍa being bhāṣāṅga and a rakti rāga one can observe many prayōgās. This facility which it developed in its texture gives a reason for being categorized as a rakti rāga.

1. **s g p m... g r s** – unusual from the pattern, the ascent in the sangati without **r** and reaching directly to **p** skipping **m**
2. **p,dn₂ d;n₃ś dp**, - this prayōga is seen in Nādōpāsana kṛti used with total freedom by Sri Tyagaraja for the word *svātantrulu* where the **d n ś** phrase is unusual to the structure of the rāga.
3. **g,mp g r s – d p m p g r s** – beyond its regular descent pattern
4. **n s d p - ṛ n d p**
5. **g m d (dpm)r s** – the usage of **g m d** with **p** varjam in ascent etc.
6. **d m , g m r**

Signature phrases of the rāga:

Apart from special prayōgās there are also many signature phrases which highlight their presence in the rāga. Those phrases will have some common patterns like consonant phrases and other special features. It should also be noted that few of the special prayōgās are also categorized as signature phrases.

1. **ṇ s g r g, - m p d p ś, - n ś ḡ ṛ ḡ,**
2. **ṁ,ṁ, ḡṛś – n,n, dpd – m,m,grs**
3. **ṛ n, d p m – d m, g m r**
4. **s g r g, - s m g m, - s p m p, - s n, d p m, g r s**
5. **g m p d n, d p**

Conclusion

Bēgaḍa rāga is with full of surprises, special sangatīs, a smooth zig zag and up down flow, including soft as well as weighty vaḷi gamakās, charming and sparkling ravva gamakās and consonant phrases, recognisable more with svara phrase patterns beyond the structure, a creamy flavoured smoothness while rendering etc, all these features made this rāga a Rakti rāga showing how emotionally very expressive it is. This study explored the identity of Bēgaḍa in its fullest sense focussing on the emotional expressions and taking the rakti nature as the base of the rāga.

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